

Did you know that cities are responsible for over 2 billion tons¹ of waste annually, much of which could be turned into valuable resources?

From food waste to wastewater and construction and demolition debris, urban areas produce a wide range of waste streams, which end up in landfills or remain improperly managed. It contributes to environmental degradation and represents a highly inefficient use of resources.

At the same time, industries continue to rely heavily on virgin materials to produce new goods at a rate that significantly exceeds the planet's capacity.

At this rate, we would need 1.7 Earths to support this demand, and we are already pushing our planet to the limit!!

United Circles is leading the change by showing how cities and industries can work together to upcycle waste into value-added products. By connecting urban and industrial systems with a set of new technologies and collaborative models (Hubs4Circularity), the project will accelerate our progress to a fully decarbonised future without waste and with closed resource and energy loops.

Our goal?

Zero-waste cities and decarbonised industries that support sustainable growth and resilient communities.

The plan?

To promote a circularity culture to tackle all generated waste across regions and industrial sectors through collaboration and innovation.

HUB SALAMANCA

Urban Waste Water (UWW)

Salamanca

HUB ANKARA

Urban Construction & Demolition Waste (C&DW)

Ankara

HUB VENETO

Urban Food Waste-Used Cooking Oil (UCO)

Veneto

<https://unitedcircles.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union